

Investigation into the effect of blade number on the efficiency of a wind turbine

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Declaration

I declare that this report and the studies described herein are my own. Other sources are all acknowledged within a bibliography. I confirm that I have not used any generative AI to create this document.

Rohan Mitra-Flynn

9th February 2025

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I would like to thank Mrs Browning and Mrs Morgan for their encouragement and support, enabling me to undertake this project within the St. Michael's STEM Club.

Thank you to the St. Michael's Physics Department for allowing me to borrow various apparatus.

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Many thanks to Professor Ian Masters and Mr Iestyn Morgan for their comments on the project.

Abstract

In the future, with the phasing out of fossil fuels, energy will be sourced renewably. One method of renewable electricity generation is wind power. However, the efficiency of a wind turbine is determined by a number of factors, including the number of blades. This investigation reports a study investigating the number of blades a wind turbine should have. A 2-bladed, 3-bladed, and 4-bladed wind turbine were compared at different wind speeds. Results showed no clear advantage between the two and three-bladed wind turbine, but the four-bladed turbine that was implemented here was less efficient. Recommendations are made for future studies.

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Introduction

Fossil fuels such as coal, gas, and oil are used widely to generate electricity all over the world (Covert et al. 2016). However, burning fossil fuels releases greenhouse gases such as carbon dioxide into the atmosphere, which contribute to climate change (Soeder 2021). Hence, countries across the globe are trying to move towards using more renewable sources of energy, such as solar power and hydroelectric power instead of fossil fuels. Currently, the most common renewable energy source in the United Kingdom is wind power, which is harvested by onshore and offshore wind turbines (Morley 2024).

History of windmills

The earliest example of wind powered machinery was described by Hero of Alexandria in his book *Pneumatica* (Circa 50 AD) (Vowles 2018). The English translation of this book describes this machinery as a “small wheel... with broad arms like the sails of a windmill... that when urged by the wind, drive round the wheel... and raise the piston” to power a wind organ (Hero et al. 1851). It was during the 7th to 9th century when Persian farmers first to put this idea to use. They used a vertical panemone wind turbine design, which works like a waterwheel on its side. The wind turbines were used to pump water and grind grain. This design became widespread throughout Asia and was used in some parts of northern Europe. However, European millers preferred to use the post mill, a four bladed design. Originally built for grinding grain, by the 1600s these windmills were also built for numerous other roles, such as wood-sawing and spice grinding. Some of the most famous examples of this design of windmill are the pumping variations that can be seen today at Kinderdijk in the Netherlands (**Fig.1**).

During the 1700s, all these windmills were gradually converted to steam power (De Decker 2009), and the use of wind power to obtain energy diminished in importance.

Figure 1: Traditional four-bladed windmills at Kinderdijk, The Netherlands

Dawn of the Wind Turbine

The 1800s were full of technological innovation, especially involving electricity such as Faraday's electric generator (1832), Edison and Swann's lightbulb (1878-79), Bell's telephone (1876). With Parson's invention of the steam turbine, a method to efficiently generate electricity was created (Bellis 2024). In this atmosphere of innovation, it was not long before someone tried to use wind power to generate electricity. In 1887, Scottish scientist James Blyth created the first wind turbine to generate electricity (Gipe et al. 2022; Anon 1). His first attempt was using a standard 4-bladed agricultural wind turbine. However, he discovered that this design would invariably spin too quickly and destroy itself. After various other design ideas, he switched to a vertical design based on the then recently invented anemometer, which did not have this problem and was successful in generating electricity. During the late 19th century, other scientists such as Charles de Goyon (France) and Charles Brush (USA) also experimented with electricity-generating wind turbines. Up until the 1920s, the main designs were modified versions of the traditional windmills.

After World War 1, aerodynamicists in Denmark began looking at using aerofoils for the blades of wind turbines, and developed the now-standard 3-bladed design. Wind turbine development continued on and off for the next 40 years, but major importance was not taken of the development until the 1970s (Gipe et al. 2023). When the world's first oil embargo occurred in 1970, aerospace companies everywhere, but especially in the USA, Germany, and Sweden, tried, and failed, to develop a large-scale wind turbine. However, what would eventually become the standard modern wind turbine design was created by Tvind School in Denmark, and since then has been adopted all over the world.

Figure 2: Timeline showing the development of wind power. Figure obtained from Anon 2

The current standard wind turbine design uses a three-blade configuration (**Fig.3**).

Figure 3: Wind turbine farm near to Penlle'r Castell, South Wales; this site is equipped with three bladed wind turbines.

There are various other configurations of wind turbines. Two-bladed and helical wind turbines have also been tested, but never put into mass usage (Jeon et al. 2015).

Aim, Objectives and Hypothesis

The optimal design of a wind turbine would be cheap to make, generate a significant amount of electricity at a range of different wind speeds and at the end of its lifetime should be easy to recycle. The **aim of this project** was to determine the best configuration of wind turbine blades to generate maximum electricity under a range of wind speeds. This aim was achieved through the completion of the objectives listed below.

1. Construction of a suite of blade assemblies to make 2-, 3- and 4- bladed wind turbines for testing using a wind turbine blade test rig consisting of a generator and an ammeter.

2. Construction and evaluation of a wind tunnel to determine whether it could provide an advantage for the project experiments.
3. Experiments to evaluate efficiency of the different wind turbine blade configurations under different wind speeds.

My hypothesis was that a 4 bladed wind turbine would be most effective at catching the wind energy, and converting it into electricity, as there are more blades to capture the wind.

Project Plan

My plan was to build scaled-down models of wind turbine blades and measure how much electricity is generated at different wind speeds for each type of blade. I would then compare the results to see which blade type generated the highest amount of electricity at a range of different speeds. I started the project on 28th February 2024 and have undertaken the work during the school STEM club which runs for 1 hour every week during the school term time. Figure 4 provides a Gantt chart of the tasks I needed to complete for this project, and the time I took to complete each task.

Figure 4: Gantt chart showing time taken to complete each section of the project. The tasks can be categorised broadly into 3 main sections: preparation (weeks 1-11; red), experimentation (weeks 12-14; blue), and data analysis and writing up (weeks 15-33).

Materials and Methods

Construction of apparatus

The two major pieces of apparatus that I needed to construct were the blades that I would be testing, and the testbed, which would consist of the generator and the framework required to support it.

Section 1: Construction of wind turbine blades

I made the wind turbine blades out of 2 L plastic bottles. In order to keep **the surface area of blades (control variable)** the same, I made the 3-bladed turbine's blades first, based off the real-world design seen in **Figure 3**. I then drew around one of the blades on graph paper and counted the number of 2 mm sided squares within the outline. This gave me a surface area of 34 cm² per blade, or a total of 102 cm² for the entire assembly. Then I made the 2- and 4-bladed turbines with rectangular blades. The surface area of each blade was 25.5 cm² for the 4-bladed turbine and 51 cm² for the 2-bladed turbine. I cut the required shapes out of these bottles and then I taped a K'NEX rod to the leading edge of each blade to strengthen it. They were then taped to Lego propellor hubs, which would allow them to be attached to the generator axle. The blade assemblies are shown in **Figure 5**.

Figure 5: The three wind turbine blade assemblies. The blades are made of transparent plastic bottles, and there is a K'NEX rod (blue) taped to the leading edge of each blade for strengthening. The blades are attached to Lego propellor hubs (black for two- and four-bladed, grey for three-bladed)

Section 2: Construction of wind turbine test rig

I originally was going to use a generator supplied by the school to connect the wind turbine blades to. However, the one supplied had too many gears causing too much resistance leading to no

activity. I then decided to make my own generator using a motor and a Lego gearbox. Instructions for the construction of this assembly are shown below in **Figure 6**. I mounted the gearbox onto a K'NEX frame. Steps 1 through to 7 are constructed out of conventional Lego bricks. The tissue seen in step 8 is used to ensure the motor, which is added in step 9, connects to the gear on the main shaft. The gear on the motor is a Lego gear, which grips to a piece of rubber tubing which is on the motor shaft. The mostly Lego generator is connected to the supporting K'NEX framework by a special K'NEX piece, which can be seen in steps 27 and 28. This piece consists of a K'NEX rod with two Technic half pins on the end, allowing it to connect to both Lego and K'NEX parts.

Figure 6: Gearbox and its supporting frame: order of assembly; additional photos in **Figure S1**

Section 3: Construction of wind tunnel

To keep the wind from the fan focused, I constructed a wind tunnel. I made the frame out of K'NEX and covered it in wrapping paper to seal it (**Figure 7**). The dimensions were 52 cm x 50 cm x 81 cm.

Figure 7: The Wind Tunnel. The fan is located on the left-hand end, and a meter ruler is shown for locating the test turbine; additional photos in **Figure S2**.

Methods

Section 1: Testing usefulness of the wind tunnel

Figure 8: Set-up of the apparatus. Behind the fan is a meter ruler for locating the clamp stand

To carry out this experiment, I used a 3-speed fan (diameter: 51 cm) to supply the airflow. To measure the airflow speed, I used a handheld anemometer (Skywatch Atmos; JDC) attached to a retort stand. I placed this central relative to the fan, at a distance of 10 cm from the fan, and measured the wind speed. I then moved the stand back 20 cm, and recorded the wind speed again. I continued to do this until the anemometer was 70 cm away from the fan. I then repeated the whole experiment, but with the wind tunnel constructed in *Materials Section 3*.

Section 2: Evaluation of the efficiency of the different wind turbine blade configurations under different wind speeds

Figure 9: Set-up of the apparatus. Behind the fan is a meter ruler for locating the test turbine

To perform this experiment, I used the fan described in *Methods Section 1*, the wind turbine blades constructed in *Materials Section 1*, and the wind turbine test rig constructed in *Materials Section 2*. I attached the two bladed assembly to the test rig. I then placed the test rig central relative to the centre of the fan, at a distance (hub to hub) of 10 cm, and recorded the current generated on an ammeter. I then moved the test rig back in 20 cm intervals to a maximum distance of 90 cm, and recorded the current on each occasion. I repeated the above process three times in total. I repeated the whole experiment with each of the three wind turbine blade assemblies.

Wind speed setting on the fan: I kept this at the highest speed so that even when the turbine is 90 cm from the fan, the blades will have the energy to turn.

Results

Initial testing of the wind tunnel, which was intended to provide a steady wind speed over distance, showed that, although this aspiration was met between 10 and 30 cm (**Figure 10**), at greater distances from the fan, the wind speed dropped rapidly. In contrast, without the tunnel, after an initial decrease until 30 cm, the wind speed remained fairly constant. A contributing factor to the failing of the wind tunnel may have been that the sides of the wind were panting, and the frame was distorting. From these results, I decided to proceed without the wind tunnel.

Figure 10: A plot showing how wind speed varies as the distance from the fan increases with (red) and without (green) the wind tunnel.

Following from the results shown in Fig. 10, I conducted more thorough investigation without the wind tunnel, going out to a maximum distance of 90 cm from the fan. I found a linear relationship between distance from the fan and windspeed (**Figure 11**):

$$speed = -0.1155 \cdot distance + 26.435 \quad R^2 = 0.9879.$$

Figure 11: Plot showing how wind speed changes as distance from the fan increases.

Testing of the different wind turbines produced the results shown in **Figure 12**. The current generated by the two-bladed wind turbine was constant on the first two readings, and then increased at a steady rate for the next three readings (**Top Panel, Figure 12**). The results for low wind speeds are fairly consistent, and there is increasing spread of the data at higher wind speeds, as seen on the standard deviation bars. The three-bladed wind turbine started and finished with the same readings as the two-bladed wind turbine, but the data formed a very different shaped graph (**Middle Panel, Figure 12**). The spread shows the same trend as with the results for the two bladed wind turbine, consistent at low wind speeds, and increasing as the wind speed increases. The four-bladed wind turbine also started in the same place as the other two turbines, but unlike the other two, the electricity generated peaked far lower, and at a lower wind speed. The spread shows the same trend as with the other two results, consistent at low wind speeds, and increasing as the wind speed increases. However, the increase is more rapid with the four-bladed turbine.

Figure 12: Plots showing how the current generated changed as wind speed increased for each individual blade type with standard deviation bars which have 95% confidence limits. (2 blades: Blue, 3 blades: Orange, 4 blades: Grey)

Discussion

Section 1: Testing usefulness of the wind tunnel

The wind tunnel was meant to prevent the airflow from becoming turbulent. However, as **Figure 10** shows, the wind speed in the wind tunnel was more varied than the wind speed outside of the wind tunnel. This is due to the design of the wind tunnel that I used. As is seen in **Figure 7**, my wind tunnel has a square cross section. It transpires this is not a good design option, as the sharp corners can cause turbulence in the wind (Göv 2021). With the benefit of hindsight, I should have used a design with a circular cross section. Furthermore, the paper that I used to cover the K'NEX frame was not sealed properly. This led to the paper billowing, which would have further increased the turbulence.

Section 2: Evaluation of the efficiency of the different wind turbine blade configurations under different wind speeds

Figure 13 brings together data shown in the separate panels of **Figure 12**. As can be seen, my hypothesis was incorrect, as the four bladed wind turbine generated the least energy out of all the turbines. This may be because the length of the blade was the shortest out of the three. This means that there was very little blade length that was not blocked from behind by the generator hub, and hence could capture the airflow.

Figure 13: A plot showing how the current generated changed as wind speed increased for all 3 blade configurations.

Also, as could be seen in **Figure 12**, there was a large deviation on several of the data points. This is most likely because I did not use the wind tunnel, and hence the airflow was less focused and turbulent further away from the fan.

Figure 14: A graph showing the wind turbine curve, accessed from Anon 3 on 29th January 2025.

Despite this, it can be seen that at least the results for the 3 bladed wind turbine match with what other investigations have found (Wagner et al. 2009; Lydia et al. 2014). **Figure 14** shows how the power generated by a wind turbine changes as wind speed increases. The shape of the curve is very similar to the shape of the results that I collected for the 3-bladed wind turbine (**Figure 13**, the orange line).

Future Work

If I was to conduct this experiment again, I would change the following factors:

- The wind tunnel: in this investigation, I did not use the wind tunnel I constructed as it did not work and hence there was a wide spread of data. To improve this, I would use a wind tunnel made out of a cylindrical container, such as an oil drum.
- The blade length: when I made the blades, I kept the total surface area the same. However, this meant that the blades were of varying lengths, and there was a large amount of the

blade that was blocked by the generator, especially on the 4 bladed turbine. To improve this, I would keep both the blade length and the total surface area the same.

- The generator size: the generator I made was constructed out of Lego and had to accommodate both the Lego gears and the motor with its large base. This led to it being large and blocking a large amount of room behind the blades. To improve this, I would use CAD-CAM software and a 3D printer to design and build a generator to be as small as possible but still function correctly.
- Additional factors to consider would include the blade pitch (Schubel et al. 2012) and aerofoil section (Schubel et al. 2012; Ferreira et al. 2023). There would also be a difference between onshore and offshore wind turbines, as offshore turbines will not have the turbulence problems of onshore turbines (Lynn 2011). Wind turbines mounted on buildings will also have different requirements to handle turbulence (Walker 2011).

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Appendix A: Raw Data

Distance from fan compared to Wind speed: plotted in Figure 12

Distance from fan(cm)	Wind speed (m/s)
90.00	16.2
70.00	19
50.00	20
30.00	23
10.00	26

Wind tunnel experiment data: plotted in figure 10

Distance from fan(cm)	Wind Speed (Km/h)	
	With Tunnel	Without Tunnel
10	21.0	21.5
30	23.0	15.0
50	14.9	14.5
70	10.3	14.1

Results for main experiment

Data collected for two-bladed wind turbine

Distance (cm)	Current(A)				
	1	2	3	Average	Standard deviation
10	0.050	0.090	0.060	0.067	0.021
30	0.030	0.060	0.040	0.043	0.015
50	0.020	0.030	0.030	0.027	0.006
70	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.010	0
90	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.010	0

Data collected for three-bladed wind turbine

Distance (cm)	Current (A)				
	1	2	3	Average	Standard Deviation
10	0.080	0.060	0.060	0.067	0.016
30	0.070	0.040	0.050	0.053	0.015
50	0.030	0.030	0.030	0.030	0.000
70	0.020	0.010	0.020	0.0167	0.006
90	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.000

Data collected for four-bladed wind turbine

Distance (cm)	Current(A)				
	1	2	3	Average	Standard Deviation
10	0.040	0.060	0.020	0.040	0.020
30	0.050	0.070	0.020	0.047	0.025
50	0.050	0.050	0.020	0.040	0.017
70	0.020	0.040	0.010	0.040	0.015
90	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.000

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1: Additional photos of gearbox construction; see also Figure 6.

Figure S2: Additional photos of the wind tunnel; see also Figure 7.

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